

Part 1 - Original Articles - Peer-Reviewed

Section-1 : Comprehensive Articles

Use of Single Homeopathic Similimum - *Natrum muriaticum* in Treating a Case of Depressive Episode

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Abstract

A case of depressive episode was treated with individualized homeopathic medicine, *Natrum muriaticum* over a period of 8 months. The improvement in the specific symptoms demonstrated the efficacy of the homeopathic treatment, leading to complete remission of symptoms. The improvement in the case was assessed monthly using Hamilton depression Scale. HAM - D case was selected based on the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria for depressive disorder. Prior, the patient's symptoms were repertorized, and the most appropriate Homeopathic similimum - *Natrum muriaticum* in 200C potency was prescribed in the initial prescription. The patient was followed up for 8 months. The case report highlights the beneficial role of individualized homeopathic remedy *Natrum muriaticum* in managing patients with depression.

Keywords: Depressive episode, Hamilton Depression Scale (HAM - D), Homoeopathy, *Natrum muriaticum*

Introduction

Major depressive disorder is a common and complex mental illness that negatively affects how people feel, think, act, and perceive the world. Symptoms of depression can vary from mild to severe and varies from person to person. It is one of the most important contributors to the global burden of disease worldwide¹.

A depressive episode, according to the International Classification of Diseases, Eleventh Revision (ICD-11), is characterized by the co-occurrence of at least five of 10 symptoms, which must be present for the majority of the day, almost every day, for at least two weeks. A low mood or noticeably less interest or enjoyment in activities must be one of these signs. The mood disruption must cause substantial functional impairment and cannot be the result of substance or prescription side effects, grief, or another medical condition. The major symptoms are depressed mood, markedly diminished interest or pleasure in activities, reduced ability to concentrate, sustain attention or marked indecisiveness, beliefs of low self-worth or excessive or inappropriate guilt, hopelessness about the future, recurrent thoughts of death or suicidal ideation or evidence of attempted suicide, significantly disrupted sleep or excessive sleep, significant changes in appetite or weight,

psychomotor agitation or retardation, and reduced energy or fatigue².

Major depressive disorder (MDD) one of the most debilitating conditions in the world, has a substantial detrimental influence on daily living activities, quality of life, cognitive function, employment status, and productivity at work³. Depression affects an estimated 3.8% of the global population, with a prevalence of 5% among adults 4% in men and 6% in women and 5.7% in individuals over 60 years old⁴. Globally, approximately 280 million people suffer from depression. Between 2005 and 2018, the number of adults diagnosed with MDD increased from 13.7 million to 17.5 million, with the prevalence rate rising from 6.8 to 7.1%⁵. The condition is about 50% more common in women than in men. Additionally, more than 10% of pregnant women and postpartum mothers experience depression. Suicide, a severe consequence of untreated depression, claims over 700,000 lives annually. Among individuals aged 15 to 29 years, it ranks as the fourth leading cause of death worldwide⁶

Depression is a profound mental health disorder that rarely exists in isolation, often intertwining with various co morbidities that intensify its impact on an individual's well-being. It is frequently linked with anxiety disorders, bipolar disorder, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, chronic pain

syndromes, thyroid dysfunction, and autoimmune conditions, creating a complex interplay between mental and physical health. These co-morbidities not only exacerbate the severity of depressive symptoms but also hinder treatment outcomes, making early intervention crucial⁷.

A comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach, combining psychotherapy, lifestyle modifications, and homeopathy, is found effective in achieving lasting recovery. Understanding depression as a multidimensional condition highlights the need for personalized, holistic treatment strategies that nurture both the mind and body, empowering individuals to reclaim their lives from the shadows of despair. Here we present a case which highlights how homeopathy can be helpful in managing Depressive Episode.

CASE REPORT

A 25 year-old unmarried female presented to the outpatient department (OPD) with complaints of persistent sadness, a depressed mood, and generalized weakness. She reported a marked loss of interest in daily activities, a sense of emotional detachment from her surroundings, and complete social withdrawal. The patient expressed feelings of hopelessness, despair, and loneliness. She also reported recurrent suicidal thoughts with a strong intent to end her life by cutting her veins at wrist. Over the past two months, she has lost interest in her job and has been absent from her hospital duties. Additionally, she complained of insomnia, primarily due to intrusive thoughts about the future. These symptoms have been present since past three months.

HISTORY OF PRESENTING COMPLAINTS

The patient was apparently normal three months ago. The onset of her symptoms was noticed after a breakup. She had been working abroad for the past 1.5 years as nursing staff at a hospital. During this period, she developed a close relationship with a male colleague, which was started as a friendship and gradually progressed into an emotional and physical relationship. He became her main source of emotional support, and she shared her innermost feelings with him. They eventually decided to get married. However, during discussions about marriage, he revealed that he was previously married, which had not been disclosed earlier. The patient found this disclosure difficult to accept and felt unable to share it with her parents, leading to significant emotional disturbance. This led to a breakdown in trust, frequent emotional outbursts (including crying and shouting), and increasing interpersonal conflict. Her partner, in turn, became irritable and began accusing her, saying that she have immature character issues. With frequent agitations, mood swings, suicidal thoughts and sleeplessness patient was brought for consultation.

Past History: Medically, she experienced recurrent attacks of styes until the age of 12. At 15, she had on & off leucorrhoea discharge and took allopathic medication. she also had mild attacks of headaches during exposure to sunlight or heat.

Family History: Mother is hypertensive and taking allopathic medication. Father has frequent attacks of Renal Stone and known Type II DM and taking allopathic medications.

Personal History: Completed B.sc nursing from Hyderabad and worked As Staff nurse at Mumbai for 2 years and At Dubai for 1.5 years.

Physical Generals: She has a decreased appetite, feels full quickly, and experiences bloating after eating large meals. She is thirsty drinks large quantities of water, and both her bowel movements and urination are normal. She seldom sweats. Although she craves cold drinks and ice cream, consuming them causes throat pain. She prefers warm food, enjoys being fanned, and dislikes being covered. Her menarche occurred at age 11, and she has never been pregnant.

Life Space Investigation: The patient hails from an affluent family. Her father was a central government employee, and her mother worked at a bank. She is the second-born child in the family. Patients mother was transferred to farer district when the patient was 01 year old. From then patient was taken care by her paternal grandparents. Due to grandparents health issues, she was mainly looked after by a caretaker. She was more attached to her grandmother. During her schooldays she was more reserved with only few friends. She also had poor confidence with expectation of affiliation and attention from friends and teachers. Not much interested in take part extracurricular activities. She was average in her studies. Passed 10th and plus two with 85% and 70% marks respectively. She joined for Bsc nursing at Hyderabad and completed with first class marks. Soon after she applied for job and got selected in a reputed hospital and worked there for 2 years. Then she tried for DHA and scored high and was working at Dubai hospital.

General Physical Examination: The patient weighs 55 kg and height of 156cm, stable vitals and normal higher functions.

Mental Status Examination: The patient appeared well-dressed and adequately groomed. Psychomotor activity was noticeably reduced, with slowed movements and actions. Speech was characterized by a low tone, reduced volume, and diminished quantity, with a prolonged reaction time. Her mood was subjectively and objectively sad and depressed. Thought processes showed an increased flow of thoughts, dominated by hopelessness, helplessness, and suicidal ideation, along with anxiety regarding the future. Memory and concentration were found to be intact. Judgment remained normal, and insight was assessed at Grade 3.

Diagnosis: Depressive Episode–Moderate. (ICD 10 Code -F 32.1)

Table O1 – Hamilton rating Scale

Assessment of Symptoms of Depressive episode using HAM – D Scale

Items	19/12/23 Baseline	25-01-2024	22-02-2024	22-03-2024	26-04-2024	24-05-2024	28-06-2024	26-07-2024	30-08-2024 (End)
Depressed mood (0-4)	4	4	4	4	3	2	1	1	0
Feeling of guilt (0-4)	3	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	0
Suicidal ideation (0-4)	4	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
Insomnia (Early Night) (0-2)	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insomnia (Middle of Night) (0-2)	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Insomnia (Early Morning) (0-2)	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Work and Activities (0-4)	4	4	4	3	3	2	2	2	1
Retardation (0-4)	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	0
Agitation (0-4)	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anxiety psychic (0-4)	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	0
Anxiety somatic (0-4)	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	0	0
Somatic Symptoms – GIT (0-2)	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
General Somatic Symptoms(0-2)	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Genital Symptoms (Libido/Menses) (0-2)	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0
Hypochondriasis (0-4)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Weight loss (0-3)	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Insight (0-2)	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Total	36	31	28	22	17	11	6	5	1

Table-O2: Management and follow up details:

Date	Symptoms	Medicine	Remarks
			(HAM – D Scores)
19-12-23	Persistent sadness, despair of life Sleeplessness Social withdrawal Not interested in any activities Irregular in job Suicidal ideation	Natrum mur – 200/4doses, Weekly /1d EMES (1-0-0)	36
25-01-24	Sadness- reduced than before Sleep-improved (3-4 hrs) Social Interaction– improved Not interested in any activities Suicidal ideation-reduced	Natrum mur– 200/3d, 10 days/1d EMES (1-0-0)	31
22-02-24	Sadness- reduced, Occasionally feels lonely and dull affect. Sleep-improved (3-4 hrs) Not interested in any activities Social Interaction - improved Suicidal ideation- reduced	Natrum mur – 1M/2d, 15 days/1d EMES (1-0-0)	28
22-03-24	Sadness- markedly reduced Sleep-improved (5-6 hrs) Social Interaction - Improved Enjoys Gatherings with friends Enjoys TV shows. No suicidal thoughts.	Natrum mur – 1M/2d, 15 days/1d EMES (1-0-0)	22
26-04-24	Sadness – Nil Sleep-improved (5-6 hrs) Social Interaction - improved Gatherings with friends Enjoys TV shows. No suicidal thoughts	Natrum mur – 1M/ 1d, EMES (1-0-0)	17
24-05-24	Sadness – Nil Sleep –Good Started searching for a new job and new place of work. Personal productivity - improved	Sac. Lac	11
28-06-24	Sadness – Nil Sleep –Good Pleased to look for new job with exam and interview preparation. Personal productivity - improved No other complaints	Sac. Lac	6
26-07-24	Significant relief of symptoms	Sac. Lac	5
30-08-24	Significant Improvement noticed. No any physical complaints.	Sac. Lac	1

		nat-m	aur	ars	ign	phos	thuj	sulph	calc	plat	sep	verat	carc	stram	lach	merc	puls	staph	nat-s	lyc	dule	heali	arg-n	chim	psor	hyos	lac-h	cmic	nux-vi	ruta	spong	vanil	acon	ant-t	aur-mn	ber
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35
		19	16	15	15	14	13	12	12	11	11	11	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
		8	8	7	7	7	7	9	8	7	7	7	9	7	6	6	6	5	4	7	6	6	5	5	5	4	7	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	
1. MIND - AILMENTS FROM - love; disappointed	(57) 1	3	3		1		1	1	3	1	1	1	1	2		3				2			1	3		2	1			1	1		2	2		
2. MIND - AILMENTS FROM - neglected; being	(25) 1	2	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1							1		2								
3. MIND - FORSAKEN FEELING	(191) 1	2	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3			1	2	1	2		3	2	2		2	1	1		2	2		
4. MIND - DESPAIR - life, of	(12) 1			2					1																	1	1		2	3	3					
5. MIND - RESERVED	(135) 1	3	1	1	2	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
6. MIND - SUICIDAL DISPOSITION	(197) 1	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	1		1	2	1	2
7. SLEEP - SLEEPLESSNESS - sadness - from	(11) 1		2		2		2	1					2														1									
8. STOMACH - THIRST - large quantities; for	(88) 1	3		3	3		3	1				3	1	2		1					1	1	1		2		1		1	1	1	2			1	
9. GENERALS - FOOD AND DRINKS - cold drink, cold water - desire	(276) 1	1	1	3	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	3	1	1		3	1		3	2	2	2	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2		2	
10. GENERALS - SYCOSIS	(185) 1	2	1	2		1		2	2	1	3		1	1	2	1	1	3	3	2	2			3	1	1		1	1					1	1	

Figure O1 –Repertorisation Table of the case

Case analysis, remedy selection & outcome

Based on the case presentation and the severity of symptoms, a comprehensive totality was constructed. The Kentian totality was considered, incorporating factors such as "ailments from" emotional stressors, prominent premorbid personality traits, and physical generals. The fundamental miasm identified in this case was sycosis, which was integrated into the totality. During case taking, the underlying needs and significance of the illness were thoroughly understood. Appropriate advice and monitoring strategies were implemented to reduce suicidal intent and ensure patient safety. Repertorisation revealed *Natrum muriaticum* as the highest-scoring remedy. This was further supported by materia medica references and a constitutional understanding of the case, along with familial and environmental influences. *Natrum muriaticum* was prescribed, with potencies repeated and gradually increased based on symptomatic improvement and a reduction in the severity score. The Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D) was used concurrently to monitor depressive symptoms. Over a continuous follow-up period of eight months, the patient showed significant improvement and resumed normal functioning across daily life domains.

Conclusion

This case highlights the therapeutic efficacy of the potentized common salt, *Natrum muriaticum*, in the treatment of a patient presenting with depressive symptoms. It also emphasizes the

role of the homeopathic similimum in managing cases with suicidal ideation and multiple somatic complaints.

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